

Obstetric Outcome of Adolescent Pregnancy Admitted in Tertiary Level Hospitals in Chattogram

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Abstract

Background : Adolescence pregnancy is a global problem occurring in high, middle and low-income countries. Studies show that, in Bangladesh teenage mothers are more likely to experience pregnancy-related complications and maternal death compared to adult mothers because of incomplete physical growth, malnutrition, socioeconomic factors. Despite remarkable progress in health sector, teenage childbearing is highly persistent in Bangladesh mostly due to constant higher prevalence of child marriage. The study was undertaken to determine the obstetric outcome among pregnant adolescent mothers.

Materials and methods : The cross sectional study was conducted at tertiary medical college hospitals in Chittagong City Corporation over a period of 6 months (July-December 2014). 108 (One hundred and eight) pregnant women were included in the study. Data was collected using a pre-designed, pre-tested, semi-structured questionnaire by face to face interview method. Data was analyzed by entering it in MS Excel & SPSS 20.

Results: Most of the respondents got married below 18 years of age and mean age at the time of marriage was 16.94±1.03. Incidence of pregnancy induced anemia (61.8%) was most common antenatal complication. 46.67% had pre-term delivery and post-partum hemorrhage was the most common postnatal complication. Majority (61.1%) delivered baby through caesarian section followed by 38.9% Vaginal delivery. 69.75 newborn had complications

where prematurity and low birth weight were found most frequent neonatal outcome.

Conclusion: Adolescent pregnancy exposes to mother to many health related complications and newborn to poor birth outcome. It was associated with increased incidence of pregnancy induced anemia, gestational DM, preeclampsia, eclampsia, pre-term delivery, low birth weight.

Key words: Adolescent; Adolescent Pregnancy; ANC; APH; Maternal outcome; PPH; PRO.

Introduction

Adolescence (From latin adolescere 'to mature') is a transitional stage of physical and psychological development that generally occurs during the period from puberty to legal adulthood. Adolescence is usually associated with teenage years, but its physical, psychological or cultural expressions may begin earlier and end later¹. The period of adolescence extends from 10-19 years. The United Nations Children Fund (UNICEF), defines teenage pregnancy as "a teenage girl, usually within the ages of 13-19, becoming pregnant and refers to girls who have not reached legal adulthood, which varies across the world"².

It is considered a serious public health problem worldwide, approximately, 95% teenage pregnancy occur in developing countries³. Around the world, an estimated 15 million girls under the age of 20 years give birth, representing up to one fifth of all births⁴. The situation is more severe in South East Asian countries due to higher percentage of teenage pregnancy because of their common practice and early marriage⁵. Evidence further indicates that nearly 60% of all girls are married by the age of 18 years and one fourth is married by the age of 18 years and one fourth is married by the age of 15 years in South Asia, whereas within South Asia, the recorded adolescent pregnancy rate is highest in Bangladesh (35%) followed by Nepal (21%) and India (21%)⁶. According to health Bulletin 2014, the adolescent (10-19year) constitute about 23% of

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the population in Bangladesh. About 50% of all 15-19 years old females are married, of whom about 33% are already mothers, and another 6% are pregnant having risk to their health⁷. Complications during pregnancy and childbirth are the leading cause of death for 15-19 years old girls globally. Usually adolescent girls are anemic, malnourished and neglected. They become pregnant before achieving their own growth potential. Adolescent mothers (Ages 10-19 years) face higher risks of anemia, eclampsia, puerperal sepsis, prolonged labor, obstructed labor and systemic infections than women aged 20-24 years⁸.

Adolescent child bearing has emerged as a major concern in Bangladesh due to its adverse effects on both mothers and babies born to adolescent mothers. Bangladesh is one of the vulnerable countries in South Asian region regarding early motherhood risks. Early marriage is a common phenomenon in Bangladesh. Among 6 administrative divisions of Bangladesh, Rajshahi has the highest early marriage rate (81%) compared to the lowest in Sylhet (58%)⁹. Maternal mortality for adolescent is double the national figure¹⁰. The infants of adolescent mothers have a higher incidence of low birth weight, prematurity, still birth and perinatal mortality. Low birth weight is one of the most common problems in adolescent pregnancy and majority of these LBW babies is due to intrauterine growth retardation. LBW survey 2004 reported that in Bangladesh, more than one out of every three children, or 1.03 million babies each year, is born with low birth weight. Hence in this background, this study is conducted at two tertiary medical college hospitals with the aim to study the obstetric outcome associated with teenage pregnancy.

Materials and methods

This cross sectional descriptive type of study was conducted at the Department of obstetrics and Gynecology, Chittagong Medical College Hospital and Chattogram Maa-Shishu-O General Hospital in Chittagong City Corporation over a period of 6 months (July-December 2014). Two tertiary level hospitals were being selected by the investigator conveniently. All adolescent pregnant women of age between 14-19 years who had recently delivered baby in these hospitals during the study period were our target population. By using statistical formula and through non-probability type of convenient sampling 108 pregnant adolescent pregnant women were enrolled in this study following

the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The first contact with the study participants for data collection began immediately after delivery of the baby. The study participants were interviewed by using pre-tested mixed type of questionnaire according to the schedule as soon as their condition permitted. For some information, document review was also required (HB%, Blood group, Operative note, Confinement note, APGAR SCORE, birth weight) of the newborn. All the respondents were informed verbally about the purpose of the study. Full dignity and privacy was maintained in asking questions. The data was compiled, tabulated, processed in the computer according to the key variables, using statistical software IBM-SPSS version 20 for windows.

Results

Table I Distribution of respondents according to age at marriage

Age □	Frequency□	Percentage (%)
<18 years□	72□	66.67%
≥18 years□	36□	33.33%
□	108□	100.00%
Age at the time of marriage□	Mean ±SD□	Range
□	16.94±1.03□	15-19

The mean age at the time of marriage was 16.94 (SD±1.03) years. Majority of the respondents 72(66.67%) were got married < 18 years of age and 36(33.33%) of women were got married ≥ 18 years of age.

Table II Status of receiving antenatal care

Status of ANC□	Frequency□	Percentage (%)
Irregular□	91□	84.26%
Regular□	17□	15.74%
Total□	108□	100.00%

91(84.3%) received irregular ANC. Only 17(15.7%) received regular ANC.

Table III Distribution of respondents according to obstetric complications

Obstetric Complication□	Frequency□	Percentage (%)
Ante partum □		
Pregnancy with anemia□	55□	61.8%
Preeclampsia□	12□	13.54%
Intrapartum		
Pre-term labor□	35□	46.66%
Prolonged labor□	10□	13.34%
Obstructed labor□	13□	17.33%
Postpartum (n=19) □		
PPH□	09□	47.36%

Pregnancy with anemia (61.8%) was most common observed ante partum complication. 46.66% had preterm labor followed by 13.34% prolonged labor, 17.33% obstructed labor. 47.36% were suffering from PPH.

Figure 1 Distribution of respondents according to mode of delivery

61.1% pregnant mothers delivers through cesarean procedure followed by 38.9% vaginal delivery.

Figure 2 Distribution of respondents according to live birth and still birth

Table IV Type of complication among 69 born

Complications of baby (n=69)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Prematurity	35	50.7%
Jaundice	19	27.5%
Convulsion	05	07.2%
Congenital anomalies	01	01.5%
Others	09	13.1%

Discussion

Teenage Pregnancy is an important public health problem worldwide. It often occurs in the context of poor social standards. According to WHO, seven countries mainly constitute for half of adolescent births, name, Bangladesh, Brazil, The Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, India, Nigeria and the united states of America. The cross sectional study was carried out to explore the outcome among pregnant adolescent mothers who admitted in the department of gynecology and obstetrics in Chittagong Medical College and Chattogram Maa-Shishu-O General Hospitals in Chittagong. It is found that; majority of the respondents belongs to age group 15-19 years. In this study, most of the respondents 81.48% were Muslim. This is a reflexion of majority of inhabitants of Bangladesh. Only 44.44% respondents completed primary level of education. Out of 108 respondents, majority 75% were homemakers. In a study by Dhoddihal et al at Belgaum, near 90% respondents were noted to be homemakers¹¹. Large portion of them came from lower class and lower middle class which is similar to a study done by Nessa et al¹². Most of the respondents got married below 18 years of age and mean age at the time of marriage was 16.94 ± 1.03 . Although for girls, legal age for marriage in Bangladesh is 18. Majority of the respondents 71.30% had first child birth ≥ 18 years of age followed by 28.70% had first child birth < 18 years of age. 89.8% pregnant adolescents shared that; their pregnancy was unplanned which is similar to a study where 90% pregnancy was unplanned. 74% had no history of abortion. One alarming thing is revealed from the study that; 84.26% respondents took irregular antenatal checkup as they were unaware about the importance of checkup during antenatal period. These findings are similar to a study conducted by Sultana et al showed that teen mothers are less likely to receive timely prenatal care and they have higher rate for certain risk factor for poor pregnancy outcome¹³. In the study, incidence of pregnancy induced anemia (61.8%) was most common antenatal complication which is correlated with other study. Preeclampsia contributing in 13.54% which is correlated with study done by Parra-Pingel PE et al. 46.66% respondents had suffered from pre-term delivery followed by 17.33% obstructed labor, 13.34% perineal tear. Caesarian section was the major route of delivery among teenage mothers compared to vaginal delivery. The

finding is not similar to a study done by Hoque et al where caesarian delivery rate was significantly higher among adult mothers compared to adolescent mothers¹⁴. Most of adolescent pregnancy cases were not enlisted and came to hospital in labor condition with complications because of irregular antenatal care and limited knowledge about pregnancy and labor process. Neonatal outcome was not satisfactory among teenage mothers. 50.7% newborn had prematurity followed by 27.5% neonatal jaundice, 7.2% convulsion which is correlated with study done by Aung SH. 52.53% new born had normal birth weight and 47.47% had low birth weight. This finding was different to a study conducted by Usta et al and found that teenage mothers had a significantly higher incidence of low birth weight than in the adult mothers¹⁵.

The study revealed that, adolescent pregnancy outcome was not satisfactory and early marriage, age at conception, illiteracy, social class, age old traditions, lack of knowledge about family planning are significantly associated with adverse outcome of pregnancy among adolescence.

Conclusion

Adolescence motherhood is a major global issue due to wide range of health impacts and socio-economic consequences both for mothers and children. Present study recommends that in order to improve the teenage health multidimensional strategies should be undertaken. Increase age at marriage, public awareness, increasing access to sexual and reproductive health, in-depth studies about motherhood and ANC camp can play a significant role to minimize adverse obstetric complications, maternal and neonatal mortality and morbidity.

Disclosure

Both the authors declared no conflicts of interest.

References

1. World Health Organization, World health Statistics, World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland. 2014.
2. United Nations Children's Fund. The state of the world's children. Maternal and newborn health, UNICEF. 2008&2009.
3. Ganchimeg T, Ota E, Morisaki N, Laopaiboon M, Lumbiganon P, Zhang J, Yamdamsuren B, Temmerman M, Say L, Tuncalp O. Pregnancy and childbirth outcomes among adolescent mothers; a World Health Organization multicounty study. An international journal of obstetrics and gynecology. 2014;121(s1):40-48.
4. Darroch J, Woog V, Bankole A, Ashford LS. Adding it up: Costs and benefits of meeting contraceptive needs of adolescents. New York: Guttmacher Institute. 2016.
5. Acharya DR, Bhattarai R, Poobalan A, Van TE, Chapman G. Factors associated with teenage pregnancy in South Asia: A systemic review. Health Science Journal. 2010;4:1-13.
6. Mehra S, Agrawal D. Adolescent health determinants for pregnancy and child health outcomes among the poor. Indian Paediatrics. 2004;41:137-45.
7. Bangladesh Health Bulletin 2014. (Accessed 12 Sep 2014).
8. Neal S, Matthews Z, Frost M et al. Childbearing in adolescents aged 12-15 years in low resource countries: a neglected issue. New estimates from demographic and household surveys in 42 countries. Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand 2012;91:1114-1118.
9. Akter S, Rahman MM. Direct and Indirect Effects of Socioeconomic Factors on Age at First Marriage in Slum Areas, Bangladesh. Chinese J Population, Resources and Environment .2009; 7(3):79-82.
10. Hossain MMG et al. A study on Nutritional Status of the Adolescent Girls at Khagrachari District in Chittagong Hill Tracts, Bangladesh. American Journal of Life Science. 2013;1(6):278-282.
11. Dhoddihal CR, Katti SM, Mallalpur MD. Teenage pregnancy outcome in a rural area of South India; A prospective study. Int J Med Public Health. 2015;5:29-33.
12. Nessa K, Zebunnesa M, Bari N, Saleh AB. Study of some sociodemographic Factors in Teenage Pregnancy. Chattagram Maa-o-Shishu Hospital Med Coll J. 2014;13(3):21-25.
13. Sultana N, Chowdhury BS, Parvin T, Huq RS. Teenage pregnancy and its outcome in Bangladesh; Has the situation improved? 2015.
14. Hoque ME, Towbola OA, Mashamba TJ, Monokoane T. Comparison of adverse pregnancy outcome at a tertiary hospital in South africa. Biomed. 2014;25(2):167-172.
15. Usta IM, Zoorob D, Nassan G, Nassar AH. Obstetric outcome of teenage pregnancy compared with adult pregnancies. Acta Obstet Gynecol. 2008;87:178-83.